

FeedBag Dashboard

Hello, thank you very much for participating in this survey.

We are Timothy Zemp, Severin Siffert and Sarah Zurmühle, a group of students studying Computer Science at the University of Zurich. We are currently working on a project featuring the creation of a dashboard for the FeedBag application. FeedBag is an extension for Microsoft's Visual Studio created by the KaVE Project (<http://www.kave.cc/>). It tracks all activities performed inside Visual Studio, e.g. mouse movements, pressing a key on the keyboard, and every command given to Visual Studio. The data is stored anonymously.

For now, FeedBag's tracked data is available to the users, however only looking at the raw data might not provide you with valuable insights in your coding behavior. We intend to use this raw data to create useful visualizations which will bring more benefits for our users. To accomplish this goal, we plan to implement a personal productivity dashboard which visualizes the users' activities. This will help our users to find good and bad habits so they can become more productive.

To ensure that our dashboard will be valuable for users, we would like to get some feedback from professional developers on the following mockups that demonstrate the features of our dashboard. You do not need to know the FeedBag application to continue.

This survey is anonymous, no personal information will be collected. We would greatly appreciate your participation in this survey. The survey should take no longer than 15 minutes. Thank you!

If you would like to contact us, please write us an e-Mail: proksch@ifi.uzh.ch

* **Erforderlich**

Demographic Questions

1. **How did you find this survey (e.g., "personal contact", "forum X", "r/catlolz", ...)?**

2. **How old are you?**

3. **What is your gender?**

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- Female
- Male
- Other
- Prefer not to say

4. What is your highest degree?

5. Which of the following best describes your role?

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- Individual contributor
- Lead
- Manager
- Other

6. What is your main programming language?

7. How many years of professional coding experience do you have?

Mockup Overview

We intend to create a dashboard which visualizes your activities inside the IDE Visual Studio to help you to better understand your coding behaviours. Our dashboard will be integrated in Visual Studio as a menu bar entry. When you click the dashboard menu entry, a browser will be opened and you'll see the dashboard start screen.

The following mockups will present you how we intend to structure our dashboard.

As you can see below, the dashboard consists of four sections:

- Activities
- Testing
- Global Statistics
- Data Exploration.

In a later stage of this survey, we will show you in detail what information is being visualized for each of these sections.

You can either click on the icons to go to the corresponding section, or open a side menu by clicking on the three horizontal lines on the upper left corner of the screen. If you do the latter option, you see a side menu like the one in the picture below. You may have noticed, that the sidebar includes a username, user-ID and a user picture. The users should be able to create an individual account, to make it easier for you to get access to your personal data. Your account is anonymized, so that no personal information is being stored.

To go to your desired section, you can use the side-menu entries. The sections do not have subsections, except for the activity section. As you can see below, the activities are grouped into "Which Activities" and "Activity Locations". The "Which Activity" subsection visualizes what type of activities you performed and the "Activity Locations" subsection presents where you performed your activities. We will show you how these subsections are going to look like in a later stage of this survey.

This is a rough explanation how the dashboard is structured. In the following questions, we will focus on the visualizations themselves.

Activity Section

The activity sections feature all your tracked activities. We separate between two different kind of subsections:

- 1) What were your performed activities?
- 2) In which part of the system did you perform these activities?

In the two short videos below, we demonstrate how we interactively visualize these two subsections. Please watch them and answer the questions below. To open the videos in full screen, click on the YouTube symbol. This will open the video in a bigger version in a separate browser tab.

1. Activity Types

<http://youtube.com>

[/watch?v=cQcTsDgueAE](http://youtube.com/watch?v=cQcTsDgueAE)

8. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval pro Zeile.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	No Answer
The visualizations are understandable.	<input type="radio"/>					
The visualizations are useful.	<input type="radio"/>					
I would use this part of the dashboard.	<input type="radio"/>					

9. Do you have additional comments or ideas on this part of the dashboard? (Optional)

2. Development Locations

<http://youtube.com>

[/watch?v=6pLq91UntTg](http://youtube.com/watch?v=6pLq91UntTg)

10. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval pro Zeile.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	No Answer
The visualizations are understandable.	<input type="radio"/>					
The visualizations are useful.	<input type="radio"/>					
I would use this part of the dashboard.	<input type="radio"/>					

**11. Do you have additional comments or ideas on this part of the dashboard?
(Optional)**

Testing

The testing section visualizes your testing behavior. We separate between written tests and completed test driven development cycles (definition see below). We will present you how we intend to visualize these two test metrics below.

Written Tests

Have you ever wondered how much you tested your code in the previous weeks? Or have you ever been curious in which weeks or months you were the most eager in writing tests? If that is the case, the testing section might come in handy. It reminds you how much you did to keep your codebase well tested. This section shows you how many test you wrote each day. Your testing behavior is visualized with a heatmap where a darker color means that you wrote more tests (only the amount of written tests is taken into account, there is no correlation with other coding related metrics, like e.g. written methods). For instance, in the example visualization below you can see that there are weeks (e.g. week #22 or #23) where not many tests were written in comparison to other weeks (e.g. week # 11 or #12).

12. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval pro Zeile.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	No Answer
The visualization is understandable.	<input type="radio"/>					
The visualization is useful.	<input type="radio"/>					
I would use this part of the dashboard.	<input type="radio"/>					

13. Do you have additional comments or ideas on this part of the dashboard?
(Optional)

Test Driven Development cycles

Defintion: Test driven development (TDD) is a process in software development. It features short development cycles which are constantly repeated. In each cycle, a requirement is written as a test and the corresponding software is then designed to pass this test. This procedure is then repeated until each requirement is fulfilled.

Have you ever asked yourself how many TDD cycles you completed over the last week or month? If that is the case, our testing section has the right visualization for you. We plan to visualize the amount of completed TDD cycles with an heatmap as well, where a darker color means that you completed more TDD cycles. For instance, the visualization below demonstrates that you completed not so many TDD cycles in week #23, but were more eager in week #20.

We identify a TDD cycle by distinguishing the process of writing/editing a test, failing the same test, then afterwards changing non-test files and finally passing the same test which concludes the cycle.

14. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval pro Zeile.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	No Answer
The visualization is understandable.	<input type="radio"/>					
The visualization is useful.	<input type="radio"/>					
I would use this part of the dashboard.	<input type="radio"/>					

15. Do you have additional comments or ideas on this part of the dashboard?
(Optional)

Global Statistics

Do you sometimes wonder how your coding behavior compares to other developers? If so, then the global statistics section is the perfect page for you. There, you can compare yourself to the global median on a lot of metrics to other users. It shows you lots of numbers, such as how much time you spent coding each day or how many tests you wrote.

Of course we will give you control in how your data is being used and stored. We will discuss the privacy handling in the next page.

	User Value	Median over all users
Activity statistics over a week		
IDE is active	95%	91%
■ Debugging	24%	22%
■ Testing	21%	19%
■ Writing Code	37%	38%
■ Reading Code	13%	12%
IDE is inactive	5%	9%
Testing statistics over a week		
Number of written test	11	23
Number of run tests	32	24
Number of fixed tests	5	12
Number of deleted tests	2	1
Coding statistics over a week		
Aggregated number of commits through Visual Studio	18	35
Number of executions/builds	55	68
Build Times	2s	0.5s

16. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval pro Zeile.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	No Answer
The table is understandable.	<input type="radio"/>					
The table is useful.	<input type="radio"/>					
I would use this part of the dashboard.	<input type="radio"/>					

17. **Do you have additional comments or ideas on this part of the dashboard?**
(Optional)

Privacy

FeedBag needs to collect sensitive data to generate meaningful statistics. However, we would like to give you control over how the data is used!

Not every project is structured the same way, so you can control the data collection for each project you work on individually. Most importantly, you can completely disable data collection for very sensitive projects. For anything else, you can select how the data can be used:

1) Level of Publication: The dashboard always needs access to all data to compute the statistics, but -being researchers- we also would like to use the collected data to understand what kind of information developers need. Optimally, we could also share this data with other researchers. Another option would be to publish your data as an open data-set. This is, like publishing your data for research, not mandatory.

2) Level of Sensitivity: The interaction data includes various information, some more sensitive than others. You will have the option to configure data usage for the different categories individually.

Your collected data is being stored locally on your computer. Only if you agree to upload your data, it will be send to our server.

The following mockup illustrates the available privacy options.

Data Collection Settings for Sample Project

Enable data collection for this solution

only for dashboard *to use in research* *publish in open data-set*

Events containing generic interaction data <i>e.g. clicks, menu navigation, build duration, ...</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Events containing project specific data <i>e.g. filenames, project names, ...</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Events containing source code	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Save

Data Collection Settings for Sample Project

Enable data collection for this solution

only for dashboard *to use in research* *publish in open data-set*

Events containing generic interaction data <i>e.g. clicks, menu navigation, build duration, ...</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Events containing project specific data <i>e.g. filenames, project names, ...</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Events containing source code	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Save

18. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval pro Zeile.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	No Answer
The privacy settings are understandable.	<input type="radio"/>					
The privacy settings are useful.	<input type="radio"/>					
I would use this part of the dashboard.	<input type="radio"/>					

19. How much of your data would you be willing to share? (Optional)

20. How much are you allowed to share? (Optional)

21. Do you have additional comments or ideas on this part of the dashboard? (Optional)

Conclusion

You are almost done! To conclude, we would like to ask you some overall questions.

22. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval pro Zeile.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	No Answer
I would use the dashboard I just saw.	<input type="radio"/>					

23. Are there any positive things that stood out? If yes, which were they? (Optional)

24. Are there any negative things that stood out? If yes, which were they? (Optional)

25. Imagine your ideal dashboard: What other statistics or metrics should this dashboard provide besides the ones already shown in this survey? (Optional)

26. It may be possible that we would like to ask you some follow-up questions specific to your answers. If you would like to answer these possible questions, please share your e-Mail address with us. (Optional)

27. Do you have any other comments or suggestions regarding this survey? (Optional)

Bereitgestellt von

